

Study protocols

Collaboration on Rare Diseases as part of the Medical Informatics Initiative (CORD-MI)

Disclaimer

*This is an excerpt from the original study protocol (as of December 21, 2020)
which was created as part of CORD-MI.*

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Financing

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<https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/de/CORD>

Background

In the project "Collaboration on Rare Diseases (CORD-MI)" of the German Medical Informatics Initiative (MII) founded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, twenty German university hospitals and other partners are committed to improving care and research in the field of rare diseases. The MII is based on the action plan of the National Action Alliance for People with Rare Diseases (German "Nationales Aktionsbündnis für Menschen mit Seltenen Erkrankungen; NAMSE), whose founding members are ACHSE e.V., the German Federal Ministry of Health and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. Each of the university hospitals in CORD-MI has a Center for Rare Diseases, is a member of one of the four MII consortia (HiGHmed / DIFUTURE / MIRACUM / SMITH) and is at an advanced stage of establishing a Data Integration and Competence Center (DIC) according to the rules of the MII.

CORD-MI uses the organizational and technical solutions of the MII with the aim of improving care and research in the field of rare diseases. Data from 20 university hospitals, which will be available via the DIC, will be jointly analyzed. The aim is to prove that the IT solutions developed in the project and by the MII consortia lead to measurable benefits for patients, doctors and researchers. Furthermore, CORD-MI contributes to the overall outcome of the MII, for example by expanding medical documentation and testing innovative approaches to linking and evaluating data.

On the clinical side, CORD-MI aims to increase the visibility of rare diseases, provide insights into the reality of care, stimulate research in this area as well as evaluate and improve the quality of diagnostic and therapeutic processes. The CORD-MI project is intended to produce structures, processes and results that promote the care of people with rare diseases and research in this field locally, nationally and internationally. For the first time, data on rare diseases will be collected systematically, uniformly and interoperable in a large number of German university hospitals.

On the medical informatics side, CORD-MI focuses on improving concepts and solutions for the clinical documentation of rare diseases, on organizational, semantic and syntactic interoperability and on data protection-compliant methods for nationwide data access. With this in mind, CORD-MI is piloting and evaluating a number of solutions and then developing proposals for improvement that will be made available to a larger national and international community.

The project sees itself as a learning system. It works step by step and builds on the continuous progress of the MII. Furthermore, it is developing its own management cycle in which lessons are learned from the previous steps for the subsequent ones. This applies to documentation development, data usage concepts and data protection methods. It should be possible to make fundamental use of the results in the healthcare context and subsequent research projects, as well as to develop the concepts, methods and technologies in a subsequent phase of the MII.

In the following, the clinical picture of Phenylketonuria (PKU) and the relevant clinical questions as well as the necessary methodological and data-technical procedure are described.

Phenylketonuria (PKU)

Thanks to comprehensive newborn screening programs and optimized therapies, almost all those affected by PKU in Germany can be diagnosed fast and successfully treated since the end of the 1960s. The incidence in German-speaking countries is around 1:8,500 (on average) [1]. It must now be assumed that more than 2/3 of all people with PKU are over the age of 18. We can assume that around 5,000 people are affected in Germany. Nevertheless, PKU is often insufficiently known in adult medicine, especially among gynecologists, internists, neurologists and psychiatrists. As far as we know,

many of those affected no longer receive specific treatment and care. The extent and severity of possible long-term internal, neurological and psychiatric consequences are unknown. A few cross-sectional studies in adults with PKU show an increased incidence of relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric symptoms, which in individual cases have been associated with the presence of PKU and the quality and consistency of its treatment [2,3]. Larger or even systematic studies are lacking.

The most serious complication of patients with PKU treated in childhood has been known since the 1980s: Embryotoxicity in mothers with PKU who were not optimally treated during pregnancy. The affected children, who do not suffer from the metabolic disorder themselves, show severe developmental and organ damage depending on the quality of maternal treatment during pregnancy.

Questions

In the planned data query, the diagnosis of classic PKU and Other Hyperphenylalaninemias are to be compared anonymously with the frequencies of the internal diseases asthma, chronic angina pectoris, diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, pathological bone fragility or osteopenia, chronic kidney diseases stage I-V, degenerative diseases of the nervous system, circumscribed brain atrophy and/or depressive illnesses that may be more common in these people. Furthermore, a connection between PKU and the birth of a child is to be sought and then, if anonymized, obvious childhood diseases such as microcephaly or heart defects are to be quantitatively evaluated at birth.

Primary question

How often are relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric diseases documented in combination with PKU?

The respective frequencies of the combinations of the diagnosis codes E70.0 or E70.1 with the diseases listed in Table 1 (e.g. number of E70.0 or E70.1 AND N.18.1-5). Only one AND link is provided in each case.

The study is based on patient-related data from 2015 to 2021.

Secondary question

[A] How often do relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric diseases occur in combination with PKU relative to the total number of patients with PKU?

The relative frequency of a combination of PKU with one of the aforementioned diseases is relevant for estimating the need for care in Germany. For this purpose, the frequencies determined for the primary research question are related to the total number of patients with PKU at the respective university hospital and across the participating university hospitals.

[B] Is the relative frequency of a combination of PKU and relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric disease depending on age?

It can be assumed that the diseases mentioned are more likely to be observed in adults in addition to PKU. Therefore, the evaluation described under [A] should also be carried out separately in the age groups <18 years, 18-30 years and >30 years.

[C] How often do complications occur during pregnancy and delivery?

The respective frequencies of the combinations of the diagnosis codes E70.0 or E70.1 for PKU with a code for delivery (e.g. O80) and one of the ICD codes listed in Table 3 for a complication (e.g. O84.x) (e.g. number of E70.0 or E70.1 AND (O80 or O81 or O82 or O30.x) AND O75.x). There is only one AND link between birth in a person with PKU and a complication.

The study is based on case-related data for the years 2015 to 2021.

[D] Which child outcomes can be observed?

The following Table 4 as well as the categorical frequencies (gestational age, birth weight, length and head circumference of the child) in combination with ICD E70.0 or E70.1 of the mother. The variables are not linked to each other.

The study is based on case-related data from the perinatal survey for the years 2015 to 2021.

The determined frequencies of all questions are to be set in relation to German reference data, including health reporting.

Only some of the sites are able to establish the link between a delivering mother and the newborn in the DIZ or to provide all the data on the child required for the secondary question on child outcome ([D]). This question can therefore only be addressed by some of the participating centers.

Study-related measures / course of study

As existing data records are evaluated, there are no additional measures or increased time expenditure for patients.

The study described here is a retrospective cross-sectional survey of the years 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021, based exclusively on data already collected. All patients who can be identified in the local DIC on the basis of the ICD codes described above are included. The analyses are carried out in the same way in all participating university hospitals. The results are initially evaluated locally. If there is a data protection-compliant solution in place (see below) and after renewed consultation with the local ethics committees (amendment), it is planned to merge the data centrally in the sense of a multicenter design.

Clarification

In this study, the data is extracted without obtaining consent, so there is no informed consent process.

Data protection concept

The names of patients and all other confidential information are subject to medical confidentiality, the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the provisions of the State/Federal Data Protection Act (LDSG/BDSG).

In general, the study data is anonymized as soon as this is possible according to the research purpose. Only anonymized data is merged across the participating sites.

If study results are published, patient data is also published anonymously.

The source data is only accessible to the study team. All data will be stored without further notice for up to 10 years after the end of the project.

Effect / Benefit

This study will have no impact on the patients' diseases. There will be no direct personal benefit for the individual patients, but the study should lead to a better understanding of the diseases, which could also be of benefit to individual patients in the future.

Burden / risks

As only anonymized data is evaluated retrospectively as part of this study, there is neither a burden nor a risk for the patients as a result of the study. As a rule, patients will not be aware of the evaluation of their data as part of this study.

Accompanying therapy

The study has no influence on the therapy / concomitant therapy of the patients.

Methodology

Required data from the DIC

To assess comorbidities of PKU, the data will be evaluated on a patient-specific basis, taking into account the ICD-10-GM codes of both outpatient and inpatient presentations. The aim is to investigate whether comorbidities were ever coded for a person with phenylketonuria in the observation period 2015 - 2021. In addition to the total number of individuals with PKU, the number of patients with a comorbidity should be counted.

Table 1. Comorbidities in patients with PKU

ICD-10-GM code	Description
N18.1-5	Chronic kidney disease, stage I - V
G31.9	Degenerative disease of the nervous system, unspecified
G31.0	Circumscribed brain atrophy
F32.x	Depressive episode
F33.x	Recurrent depressive episode
F34.x	Persistent affective disorder

Table 2. Additional data included in the analysis for patients with PKU

Age	< 18 years, 18 ... < 31 years, ≥ 31 years
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With regard to the observations on pregnancy and birth in women with PKU, all inpatient cases in the years 2015-2019 are identified in which a birth (O80, O81, O82) was coded in addition to PKU (E70.0

and E70.1). These cases are counted cumulatively and the frequency of complications in the woman giving birth and the infant outcome parameters are summarized according to the following table.

Table 3. ICD codes included in the analysis for patients with PKU

	ICD-10-GM code	Description
Mother	O80	Spontaneous delivery of a singleton
Mother	O81	Birth of a singleton by forceps or vacuum extraction
Mother	O82	Birth of a singleton by incisional delivery
Mother	Z37.x	Result of the delivery
Mother	O30.x	Multiple pregnancy
Mother	Z38.x	Live births by place of birth
Mother	O64.x	Obstacle to birth
Mother	O09.x	Duration of pregnancy
Mother	O75.x	Other complications during labor and delivery
Mother	O24.4	Diabetes during pregnancy
Mother	O63	Protract birth

The following Table 4 and Table 5 summarize the additional data that can only be provided by the DIC at some locations.

Table 4. ICD codes included in the analysis for newborns of patients with PKU

Child data that can be assigned to the mother data:		
Child(ren)	E70.1	Phenylalanine embryopathy
Child(ren)	P05.x	Intrauterine deficiency development and fetal malnutrition
Child(ren)	P07.x	Disorders associated with short duration of pregnancy and low birth weight
Child(ren)	P95	Fetal death of unspecified cause
Child(ren)	Q02	Microcephalies
Child(ren)	Q24.x	Congenital heart defects

Table 5. Additional data included in the analysis for patients with PKU

Mother	Age	< 18 years, 18 ... < 28 years, 28 ... < 38 years, ≥ 38 years
Child data that can be assigned to the mother data:		
Child(ren)	Gestational age	categorical (20th - 25th week of pregnancy, 26th - 33rd week of pregnancy, 34th - 36th week of pregnancy, 37th - 41st week of pregnancy,
Child(ren)	Birth weight of the child	categorical: 500 - 749g, 750 - 999g, 1000 - 1249g, 1225 - 1499g, 1500 - 1999g, 2000 - 2499g, 2500 - 2999g, 3000 - 3999g, 4000 - 4499g, ≥ 4500g
Child(ren)	Length of the child	categorical: < 40cm, 40 - < 45cm, 45 - < 50cm, 50 - < 55cm, ≥ 55cm
Child(ren)	Head circumference of the child	categorical: < 31cm, 31 - < 33cm, 33 - < 35cm, 35 - < 37cm, ≥ 37cm

Study type

This is an open, uncontrolled, non-randomized, national, multicenter study.

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria defined for the study are:

- Confirmed diagnosis of PKU.
- No age restriction.

Exclusion criteria

None

Safety laboratory

Not required

Termination criteria

- Individual: None
- Entire study: None

Randomization procedure / plan

There is no randomization in this study.

Statistical analysis

A purely descriptive description of the variables listed above and their simple AND linkage in the form of frequencies or proportions is provided. In addition, the project evaluates the MII instruments by determining the completeness and data quality of the data available in the DIC.

Due to the purely descriptive approach, there is no biometric justification for the number of cases.

Local data analysis

The results are initially evaluated locally at each participating location. For the joint analysis, the data must be available in the form of frequencies (number). For this purpose, the continuously distributed variables birth weight, gestational age, etc. are categorized (e.g. birth weight < 1500g, 1501 - 2,500g, etc.) and the frequency in each category is determined.

Merging the data

Only anonymized data is merged across the participating locations.

Since there can also be very low frequencies (<5) at a location, individual patients could lead to the identifiability of individual persons if the numbers of each location were transferred directly to a common database.

If the research question allows, groups containing less than 5 individuals can be combined with appropriate groups containing $n > 5$ individuals (forming groups of ICD codes or not stratified by age or sex).

If such a solution is not possible due to the issue at hand, the data will be merged. A data protection-compliant solution will be developed on the basis of the knowledge gained locally and submitted subsequently. Until then, the data will only be analyzed locally at the participating locations.

Central data evaluation

For the purpose of this study, the data is to be imported locally into a standardized evaluation database in pseudonymized form at each location. The data elements used are described in

Data protection / data flow / collection and handling of clinical data

Data management in the data integration centers of the MII follows defined and standardized processes, which are set out in principle in the applicable data protection concepts and procedural rules of the respective consortium and locations.

The initial data use and data protection concept of the CORD-MI joint project in the version dated May 24, 2020, on which the TMF e.V. data protection working group issued a positive statement on May 30, 2020, is aligned with this. For the set-up phase of CORD-MI, the concept provides for a restriction to so-called “decentralized analyses”, whose aggregated local partial results are only merged centrally if they do not allow conclusions to be drawn about individual patients.

For the study, CORD-MIÄs data use and data protection concept provides for the following for each question in turn

- (1a) Local preparations in the DIC (= provision of MII core data set),
- (1b) provision of frequencies from other data sources (e.g. German Cystic Fibrosis Registry, PIMS Survey) to check data quality,
- (2a) an iterative creation of central scripts taking into account the results of the local data quality check results,
- (2b) the controlled execution of the centrally created scripts at all locations (= controlled remote data processing of the MII core data set), with local retention of the results, and
- (3) provided that a data protection-compliant solution is available (see above): Central meta-analyses by merging the decentralized (partial) results

before.

Re (1): The local preparations for the core dataset (1a) are congruent with the data preparation already underway in the MII to provide the basic data in the format of the MII core dataset. The collection of data from routine care takes place independently of the MII processes (1b). The legal basis at most locations is the respective state hospital law, which allows hospitals in general or university hospitals in particular to conduct their own research with patient data from the care context. Data use and data protection concepts as well as organizational and technical measures must be guaranteed at all locations. Clarification and facilitation must take place locally. The participating sites are provided with (i) a CORD-MI sample entry for the local processing directory and (ii) a sample data protection impact assessment.

Regarding (2): Controlled remote data processing means that a cooperative task force creates a script for each question using data structure files, which is executed locally at all locations remotely from the task force. The anonymity of the aggregated results must also be checked at the site. No legal basis is required for the creation of the scripts. For the decentralized execution of the scripts and the examination of the (partial) results, the basis for permission must be clarified by the locations with the local data protection officers in the sense of in-house research (as 1.). The participating locations are provided with (i) a CORD-MI sample entry for the local processing directory and (ii) a sample data protection impact assessment.

Re (3): The local (partial) results are aggregated, anonymous figures with no direct patient reference. The local results at the locations are used to check whether the data is anonymous and can therefore be merged without further measures. If there is a data protection-compliant solution is available (see above) and after renewed consultation (a corresponding amendment) by the local ethics committees, the data will then be merged centrally. The participating locations will be provided with (i) a CORD-MI sample entry for the local processing directory and (ii) a sample data protection impact assessment.

Flow chart incl. schedule

The course of the project over the 24-month term starting in February 2020 is shown in Figure 1.

Aufgabenliste und Zeitplan		2020	2021	2022
WP1 Studienprotokoll, Ethik, Datenschutz				
T1.1	Iterative Entwicklung von Studienprotokollen für die COD-Beobachtungsstudien			
	T1.1.1 Protokoll für die Studie über Mukoviszidose	D1.1.1		
	T1.1.2 Protokoll zur Studie über Phenylketonurie	D1.1.2		
	T1.1.3 Protokoll für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D1.1.3		
	T1.1.4 Protokoll zur Untersuchung der isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D1.1.4	
	T1.1.5 Protokoll zur Untersuchung des POMC-Mangels			D1.1.5
T1.1.6 Protokoll für die Großpflegeüberwachung			D1.1.6	
T1.2	Iterative Entwicklung von Datenschutzkonzepten für die COD-Beobachtungsstudien			
	T1.2.1 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur Mukoviszidose	D1.2.1		
	T1.2.2 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie	D1.2.2		
	T1.2.3 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D1.2.3		
	T1.2.4 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D1.2.4	
	T1.2.5 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zum POMC-Mangel			D1.2.5
T1.2.6 Datenschutzkonzept für die großflächige Pflegeüberwachung		D1.2.6		
T1.3	Ethikgenehmigung für Studien und Veröffentlichung von Protokollen			
	T1.3.1 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über Mukoviszidose genehmigt und Registrierung	D1.3.1		
	T1.3.2 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über Phenylketonurie genehmigt und Registrierung	D1.3.2		
	T1.3.3 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry genehmigt und Registrierung		D1.3.3	
	T1.3.4 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über isolierte sagittale Nahtsynostose genehmigt und Registrierung			D1.3.4
	T1.3.5 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über den POMC-Mangel genehmigt und Registrierung			D1.3.5
T1.3.6 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Überwachung der Großversorgung genehmigt und Registrierung			D1.3.6	
WP2 Dokumentationssupport				
T2	T2.1 Formale Spezifikation für Codierwerkzeuge (ID DIACOS, 3M KODIP) und seine Integration (Agfa ORBIS, CERNER i.s.h.med, CERNER Medico, MEONA Meona, SAP IS/H)	D2.1		
	T2.2 Seine Integration (Agfa ORBIS, CERNER i.s.h.med, CERNER Medico, MEONA Meona, SAP IS/H)	D2.2		
	T2.3 Technische Lösung an den Standorten implementiert	D2.3		
	T2.4 Installierte klinische Prozesse und vollständige Dokumentation für Orpha-Nummern und Alpha-ID-		D2.4	
WP3 Datenintegration				
T3.1	Erweiterung der Module			
	T3.1.1 Erweiterung des Moduls "Fall".	D3.1.1		
	T3.1.2 Erweiterung des Moduls "Diagnose".		D3.1.2	
	T3.1.3 Erweiterungsmodul " Symptome "		D3.1.3	
T3.1.4 Erweiterungsmodul " Genealogie "			D3.1.4	
T3.2	Datenextraktions- und Integrations-Pipelines			
	T3.2.1 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über Mukoviszidose	D3.2.1		
	T3.2.2 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über Phenylketonurie	D3.2.2		
	T3.2.3 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D3.2.3		
	T3.2.4 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D3.2.4	
T3.2.5 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über POMC-Mangel			D3.2.5	
T3.3	Datenbereitstellung			
	T3.3.1 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über Mukoviszidose	D3.3.1		
	T3.3.2 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über Phenylketonurie	D3.3.2		
	T3.3.3 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit		D3.3.3	
	T3.3.4 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose			D3.3.4
T3.3.5 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über POMC-Mangel			D3.3.5	
WP4 Überwachung der Datenqualität				
T4	T4.1 Definition von Datenqualitätskennzahlen und Berichten	D4.1		
	T4.2 Halbjährliche Datenqualitätsberichte für die Datenerhebung		D4.2	D4.2
	T4.3 Vierteljährliche Datenqualitätsberichte zur Datenqualität der Integration und Bereitstellung	D4.3	D4.3	D4.3
	T4.4 Interkonsortiales Dashboard für die Datenqualität		D4.4	
WP5 Datenanalyse				
T5.1	Definition der Datenanalyse			
	T5.1.1 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Mukoviszidose	D5.1.1		
	T5.1.2 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie	D5.1.2		
	T5.1.3 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D5.1.3		
	T5.1.4 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D5.1.4	
T5.1.5 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie über POMC-Mangel			D5.1.5	
T5.2	Implementierung der Datenanalyse			
	T5.2.1 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Mukoviszidose	D5.2.1		
	T5.2.2 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie	D5.2.2		
	T5.2.3 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Morbus Fabry.		D5.2.3	
	T5.2.4 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose			D5.2.4
T5.2.5 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zum POMC-Mangel			D3.2.5	
T5.3 Implementierung einer konsortialübergreifenden Analyseplattform			D5.3	
T5.4	Datenanalyse-Ergebnisse			
	T5.4.1 Interkonsortialanalyse für die Studie über Mukoviszidose			D5.4.1
	T5.4.2 Cross-Konsortialanalyse für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie			D5.4.2
	T5.4.3 Interkonsortialanalyse für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit			D5.4.3
	T5.4.4 Cross-Konsortialanalyse für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose			D5.4.4
T5.4.5 Cross-Konsortialanalyse für die Studie über POMC-Mangel			D5.4.5	
WP6 Rollout und Verbreitung der Ergebnisse				
T6	T6.1 Entwicklung eines Vertriebskonzepts für Softwaremodule		D6.1	
	T6.2 Entwicklung einer Projekt-Website im laufenden Betrieb			D6.2
	T6.3 Organisation eines wissenschaftlichen Symposiums		D6.3	
	T6.4 Veröffentlichung der geografischen Verteilung der RD im seAtlas			D6.4
WP7 Projektleitung				
T7	T7.1 Entwicklung einer Kollaborationsplattform	D7.1		
	T7.2 Entwicklung einer Kooperationsstruktur	D7.2		
	T7.3 Halbjährliche Fortschrittsberichte für das NSG	D7.3	D7.3	D7.3

Figure 1. Gantt chart illustrating the work packages over the project duration including milestones

Reporting / Publications

All data collected is used exclusively for scientific purposes.

The findings from this research project should provide clarity about the usability of the technical and organizational possibilities of MII for care and research in the field of rare diseases. In addition, proof is to be provided that cross-consortia technical solutions for data use in the context of MII can be made available. It is planned to present these to a broad readership in scientific journals in the near future.

CORD-MI aims to increase the visibility of rare diseases, provide insights into the reality of care, stimulate research in this field and evaluate and improve the quality of current diagnostic and therapeutic processes. For this reason, the clinical results are also to be published in scientific journals exclusively in anonymized form. This ensures that it is not possible to re-identify individual patients with rare diseases. Only percentages or k-anonymized frequencies will be published.

Ethical and legal aspects

The planning, implementation and use of the project and the project results will be in accordance with the relevant ethical and scientific standards. The applicants thus undertake to comply with the requirements of the Memorandum on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice of the German Research Foundation (DFG), the Declaration of Helsinki and Memorandum III "Methods for Health Services Research" of the German Network for Health Services Research, the State and Federal Data Protection Act and the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union (EU GDPR) and the respective applicable state hospital laws in their current versions. In addition, the clinically active colleagues involved follow the professional regulations for doctors of the relevant state medical association in the current versions.

The study plan is submitted to the Ethics Committee (EC) of the University of Würzburg, appointed in accordance with state law, for consultation before the start of the study program. Once the vote of the first advisory committee is available, the votes of the local ethics committees of the participating locations are obtained. Data analysis will not begin until the written, approving vote of the ethics committees of all participating sites has been received.

The names of the patients and all other confidential information for the provision of frequencies from other data sources for data quality checks are subject to the medical confidentiality of the treating physicians and the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation and the Federal Data Protection Acts (GDPR and BDSG new) as well as the state data protection laws of the respective federal states.

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